

ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

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THE INTERNATIONAL REACH OF THE DRUG TRADE

ANNOTATION

The international scale of drug trafficking and the involvement of an increasing number of states in the global network of illegal transportation routes do not currently allow countries to clearly distinguish between producers of narcotic drugs and their consumers. The trend of expansion and spread of criminal groups in the international arena, which has been gaining momentum for a long time, is due to the fact that the reaction of the drug business to various, even the smallest changes, is many times faster than the reaction of legal business to exactly the same situations on the world market.

Key words: narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances, drug industry, migrants, UN, Afghanistan, USA, Germany, Spain, Chile, South America, Sicily, Afghanistan, Corsica, economy, drug business, production, world security.

ГИЁХВАНДЛИК ВОСИТАЛАРНИ НОҚОНУНИЙ САВДОСИНИНГ ХАЛҚАРО МИҚЁСДА ТАРҚАЛИШИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Гиёхванд воситаларнинг ноқонуний савдосига халқаро миқёсда давлатларнинг жалб этилиши ҳозирги вақтда мамлакатларга гиёхвандлик воситаларни ишлаб чиқарувчиларни ва уларнинг истеъмолчиларини аниқ ажратиш имконини бермаяпти. Халқаро майдонда жиноий гуруҳларнинг кўпайиш ва тарқалиш тенденцияси узок вақтдан бери кучайиб бораётгани, наркобизнесининг турли, ҳатто энг кичик ўзгаришларга нисбатан реакцияси бир неча баравар тезроқ эканлиги билан боғлиқ.

Калит сўзлар: гиёхвандлик воситалари, психотроп моддалар, гиёхванд воситалар саноати, мигрантлар, БМТ, Афғонистон, АҚШ, Германия, Испания, Чили, Жанубий Америка, Ситсилия, Афғонистон, Корсика, иқтисодиёт, гиёхвандлик бизнеси, ишлаб чиқариш, жаҳон хавфсизлиги.

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЕ МАСШТАБЫ ВЛИЯНИЯ НАРКОТОРГОВЛИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Международный масштаб незаконного оборота наркотиков и вовлечение все большего количества государств в мировую сеть маршрутов их нелегальной транспортировки не позволяют в настоящее время четко разграничивать страны на производителей наркотических средств и их потребителей. Набирающая обороты на протяжении долгого времени тенденция расширения, распространения преступных группировок на международной арене обусловлена тем, что реакция наркобизнеса на различные, даже самые мелкие изменения, во много раз быстрее, чем реакция легального бизнеса на абсолютно такие же ситуации на мировом рынке.

Ключевые слова: наркотические средства, психотропные вещества, наркоиндустрия, мигранты, ООН, Афганистан, США, Германия, Испания, Чили, Южная Америка, Сицилия, Афганистан, Корсики, экономика, наркобизнес, производство, мировая безопасность.

Any trade activity has a huge impact on the state of the country's economy, and also shapes the overall world economy. People who have mastered one type of activity are engaged in improving technologies in this area in order to receive more income from their labors.

Thus, the gradual spread of drug trafficking throughout the world, which grew like a snowball, became larger and larger, eventually putting not just one country (producer), but the world as a whole in a critical situation.

Describing the general influence of the drug business in the modern world, one can trace not only the harmful effects of drugs on the human psyche, but also see the other side of the effects of drugs.

Have you ever thought about the influence of the drug trade on a global level, about what drug criminals are so carefully trying to hide from prying eyes? The economic component of drug trafficking on a global market is exactly what needs to be paid attention to.

Let's turn to history to find out where the drug business comes from, where the trade began, consider other equally important issues, and also try to understand what consequences criminal organizations that create and distribute narcotic substances entail from an economic point of view.

The progressive development of the drug trade in the modern world is based on the fact that it was the drug business, one of the first criminal trades, that went beyond the national boundaries of the regions where it was a traditional trade among the local population.

This event happened at the end of the 19th century. - the beginning of the 20th century, it was from that moment that the process of globalization of economic activity began. It became one of the reasons for the growth of the drug industry and its spread throughout the world.

It was at this time, in the process of globalization, that costs for foreign economic activity decreased, but migration flows increased by leaps and bounds, and control at the borders was completely conditional.

When migrants moved, they transferred the drug use traditions familiar to their countries of origin to new territories. The emergence of the drug business on the world market has played a great role both for the further development of individual countries and for global security in general. Indeed, at present it is he who provides a significant share of the income of criminal organizations.

Today, when the production of narcotic drugs that upset the human psyche has reached incredible proportions, when transportation is carried out to all corners of the world, and sales are carried out in all different ways, it is necessary to talk about the comprehensive scale of the drug business.

The global drug trade is controlled by several major organizations from South America, Sicily, Afghanistan, Corsica and so on. They form the basis of the drug trade in the world today.

It is Afghanistan, where heroin is produced, and the American South, which exports cocaine to the world market, that account for over 50% of all the world's money earned in the drug trade by criminal organizations. The existence of international specialization in criminal drug production led to the emergence of such a term as “drug-dangerous region” [1].

The illegal drug industry operates outside the bounds of the law. Its companies are not listed on stock exchanges or rated by private accounting firms, and its performance is not regularly studied by analysts, economists or financial forecasters. The hidden nature of the global illegal drug market makes it extremely difficult to estimate its size [2].

The trend of expansion and spread of criminal groups in the international arena, which has been gaining momentum for a long time, is due to the fact that the reaction of the drug business to various, even the smallest changes, is many times faster than the reaction of legal business to exactly the same situations on the world market. This is explained by the fact that the drug business is international, comprehensive in nature and trade based on a market economy.

Agree that it is no secret that criminal organizations are valued at multi-billion dollar fortunes, so one of such large-scale groups is the drug business, because indeed, it can be considered the dominant criminal organization, since it is an extremely profitable type of activity. The activity of drug traffickers has all the advantages of a criminal economy.

Such privileges include duty-free (import of absolutely all products to different countries of the world is not accompanied by any fees (since, first of all, this is an illegal act)), lack of control, concentration of huge capital in the hands of a small group of people (activities of criminals). drug traffickers establishes a single global network, which includes absolutely all participants in drug trafficking).

An industry that generates multibillion-dollar revenues is how one can characterize the drug business, where the product produced is a drug. He, in turn, is certainly specific to the global trade market; he does not need any advertising, which would generate interest in this product, it does not need promotion among the population, because the ideal advertising layout for a drug dealer, as well as for the entire drug business, creates a certain way of life, the strictest prohibitions on the use, as well as the distribution of narcotic drugs (this factor, first of all, refers to young people, especially the younger generation aged 13-17 years, when everything prohibited generates a 100% increase in desire).

It's not without reason that there is an expression “the forbidden fruit is sweet,” the manifestation of which can be clearly seen in this area. No matter how strange it may sound, it is the prohibitions that make the drug business very profitable.

Narcotic substances have the highest prices, which are determined not by the production costs of the goods, but by the demand on the drug market, which depends not only on the narcotic substance itself, but also on the consumer, the distance from him to the place of production.

In total, global drug trafficking is estimated at approximately US\$500 billion annually, which is comparable to Spain's government budget revenue in 2015 or Chile's revenue over 10 years.

Criminal gangs make such amounts of money from trade. In the future, this money, it is clear that is not kept in the wallet of any of the drug dealers, it is sent to the global banking system, namely to its shadow sector, where the procedure for receiving income from this trade by the state is not recognized and deprives it of participation in their distribution. This money is an investment in transnational organized crime.

For example, from Internet sources you can find out what the significant difference in prices is for the production of one kilogram of opium in Afghanistan and for its sale in the United States. It ranges from 30 to 70 US dollars, i.e. 3 – 7 cents per gram. The sale is carried out in the USA for about 40 dollars. We see that the selling price is approximately 550 times higher than the production price.

Thus, according to the UN, the annual drug turnover is estimated at 317 billion dollars, and is comparable to the annual budget of a country such as Germany. This is precisely what all the activities of the drug business are based on; huge financial investments create such financial potential that is unattainable for legal business even in conditions ideal for prosperity.

Let's look at the statistics published in the media. The total amount of funds spent on the purchase of narcotic substances by Russian drug addicts alone is 4.5 billion rubles per day! Having made some calculations, we get about 1.5 trillion per year, which is comparable to the budget of the Ministry of Defense [3].

Do not forget that the drug business also creates addiction among people around the world, considering the profit of drug dealers from the sale of narcotic substances, it is important to remember how much money countries spend on combating drug addiction. So the global war on drug trafficking costs \$100 billion a year.

So, based on all of the above, based on the experience of many researchers of this problem, we can say that the drug business is certainly part of economic activity. But which one is the most interesting, because these investments make contributions of a different nature to the development of world relations, both in the economic and political sense.

The destruction of global economic security is happening due to the shadow sectors of world banks. Investments of these funds, first of all, are destructive in nature; it is known that they are spent on supplying weapons to individual countries or on the creation of terrorist organizations.

As was said in the article by Tabakov A. In “International criminal drug trafficking: economic and criminological aspect”: despite the active counteraction to transnational drug crime carried out by all states of the world, the studied branch of the shadow economy continues to function effectively [1].

Indeed, I believe that the economic side of the drug trade is known to us as much as it is profitable for criminal organizations, more than they need, they will never allow us to know. Sending money to drug traffickers makes the country from which the funds flow poor, and the ongoing concentration of large sums of money in one hand, predominantly in one territory, aggravates the situation on the world stage.

Of course, the unfair distribution of resources is an objective prerequisite for conflicts and gives rise to attempts to forcefully change the world economy, as well as the entire world order as a whole.

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